

D6.3

First batch of Practice Abstracts

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This first batch of Practice Abstracts, delivered in Month 18, has been specifically performed on each region and provided in local language, and in English. These abstracts are accessible through the EIP-AGRI database, following the EIP-AGRI template, and will also be tailored to local audiences in specific formats for publication on the AGROSUS website. Additionally, the abstracts will serve as the foundation for creating diverse dissemination materials, as factsheets, infographics, videos, or podcasts, to enhance outreach and engagement.

Deliverable Number	WP / T
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Planned Delivery Date	Actual Delivery Date
30.11.2024	30.11.2024

Type of deliverable			
R	Document, report		x
DMP	Data Management Plan		
DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.		
ETHICS			

Dissemination level			
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page))		x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement		

Revision history

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
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1. Introduction

In line with the dissemination strategy detailed in the PEDR (Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results) included in D6.2, delivered in Month 6, this initial batch of Practice Abstracts serves as a foundation for engaging stakeholders at the regional level. These abstracts offer practical recommendations derived primarily from the work conducted in WP2, which involved surveys and interviews to co-create agroecological methods tailored to different biogeographical regions and cropping groups.

2. Materials

2.1. EIP AGRI format

Following the EIP-AGRI format, this deliverable by AGROSUS presents 20 Practice Abstracts, categorized across 9 countries and 9 biogeographical regions, encompassing a variety of 3 crop types: perennial, arable and horticultural.

Table 1 First batch of practice abstracts

PA Nº	Title	Country	RSC	Crop type
1	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Artic region (Iceland)	Iceland	Artic Region	Arable
2	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological methods of weed control in the Artic region (Iceland)	Iceland	Artic Region	Horticultural
3	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control asociated to arable crops in Atlantic region (Vigo, Spain)	Spain	Atlantic Region	Arable
4	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Atlantic region (Vigo, Spain)	Spain	Atlantic Region	Perennial
5	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Boreal region (Estonia)	Estonia	Boreal Region	Arable
6	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in perennial crops in Boreal region (Estonia)	Estonia	Boreal Region	Perennial

PA N°	Title	Country	RSC	Crop type
7	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Continental region (Germany)	Germany	Continental region	Arable
8	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Continental region (Ukraine)	Ukraine	Continental region	Arable
9	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Macaronesian region (Madeira)	Madeira	Macaronesian region	Perennial
10	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in perennial crops in Mediterranean region (Valencia, Spain)	Spain	Mediterranean region	Perennial
11	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in horticultural crops in Mediterranean region (Valencia, Spain)	Spain	Mediterranean region	Horticultural
12	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Mediterranean region (Cartagena, Spain)	Spain	Mediterranean region	Perennial
13	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Pannonian region (Hungary)	Hungary	Pannonian region	Arable
14	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Pannonian region (Hungary)	Hungary	Pannonian region	Horticultural
15	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Pannonian region (Hungary)	Hungary	Pannonian region	Perennial
16	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Steppic region (Ukraine)	Ukraine	Steppic region	Arable
17	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in arable crops in Steppic region (Romania)	Romania	Steppic region	Arable
18	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method	Romania	Steppic region	Perennial

PA N°	Title	Country	RSC	Crop type
	of weed control in perennial crops (vineyards) in Steppic region (Romania)			
19	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Alpine region (Poland)	Poland	Alpine region	Arable
20	Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in arable crops in Continental region (Poland)	Poland	Continental region	Arable

Figure 1 Practice Abstract by country

Figure 2 Practice Abstract by Biogeographical region

Figure 3 Practice Abstract by type of crop

2.2. AGROSUS Template for website design

To tailor the Practice Abstracts for local audiences and publish them on the project website, a dedicated template was developed. The content will be crafted using data from the EIP-AGRI Excel, supplemented with relevant images, keywords, authorship credits, and necessary adjustments to ensure clarity and engagement. Each abstract will be made available in the local

language and in English. Partners are encouraged to translate the abstracts into additional project languages to maximize impact and reach.

Figure 4 Practice Abstract template page 1 and 2

3. Annex

EIP-AGRI Common format for interactive innovation projects

The interactive innovation approach under the European Innovation Partnership Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI)^[1] fosters the development of demand-driven innovation, turning creative new ideas into practical applications thanks to interactions between partners, the sharing of knowledge and effective intermediation and dissemination.

The EIP **common format** consists of a set of basic elements characterising the project and **includes one (or more) "practice abstract"**(s). The format was developed with two main objectives:

- (1) to enable contacting partners and incentivise efficient knowledge exchange, and
- (2) to disseminate the results of the project in a concise and easy understandable way to practitioners.

The common format allows providing information all along the life-cycle of the project. The **content of the common format can be updated at any moment** when useful, for instance in an intermediate phase of the project. Project information should at least be available at the beginning (describing the situation at the start of the project, including project title and objectives) and at the end of the project (describing the results/recommendations resulting from the project, including a final project report and one or more practice abstracts).

The **common format** consists in obligatory, recommended and optional elements. Its fields are listed in the bullets below.

1) Obligatory elements

- **Title** of the project in native language: short and easily understandable (one key sentence on the project; max 150 characters, word count – no spaces)
- **Title** of the project in English: short and easily understandable (one key sentence on the project; max 150 characters, word count – no spaces)
- **Editor** of the text: person/organisation responsible for delivering the text
- **Project coordinator** (lead-partner) according to the cooperation/consortium agreement: name, address, e-mail, telephone
- **Project partners**: name, address, e-mail, telephone, type of partner (farm holder, advisor, research institute, SME, NGO, or other)
- **Keyword-category** (to be chosen from a pre-defined list of categories)
- **Project period** (starting date, end date)
- **Project status**: ongoing (after selection of the project) or completed (after final payment)
- **Main funding source** (Rural development programme, H2020, or other EU, national/regional or private funds)
- **Total budget** of the project
- **Geographical location** where the main project activities take place: NUTS 3 level, to enable contacting within/between a climatic/regional entities
- **Final report** (in the form of an annex), including a substantial description of the results - obligatory once the project is completed – to be drafted according to the requirements specific for the funding source
- **Practice "abstract"**:
 - **Objective** of the project in native language: what problems/opportunities does the project address that are relevant for the practitioner/end-user, and how will they be solved? - (300-600 characters, word count – no spaces)

- **Objective** of the project in English: what problems/opportunities does the project address that are relevant for the practitioner/end-user, and how will they be solved? - (300-600 characters, word count – no spaces)
- **Short summary for practitioners** in native language on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

2) Recommended elements

- **Description of project activities** in native language: (max 600 characters, word count – no spaces): short summary highlighting main project activities.
- **Description of project activities** in English: (max 600 characters, word count – no spaces): short summary highlighting main project activities.
- **Short summary for practitioners** in English: short summary according to guidance (see box above under "practice abstract"; 1000-1500 characters, word count - no spaces)
- **Audiovisual material** which is useful and attractive for practitioners (e.g. YouTube link, videos, other dissemination material)
- **Website** of the project (URL)
- **Links to other website(s)** hosting information on the project (results) that are available after the project has ended, by preference using the existing local/regional/national communication channels that practitioners most often use.

3) Optional elements

- [additional fields are available for additional practice abstracts]: **Practice "abstract"** in native language: short summary according to the guidance in the text box above (max. 1500 characters, word count – no spaces)]
- [additional fields are available for additional practice abstracts]: **Practice "abstract"** in English: short summary according to the guidance in the text box above (max. 1500 characters, word count – no spaces)]
- **Description of the context of the project** (e.g. drivers in legislation/ markets or other causes that were at the origin of the project, etc.)
- **Additional information** on the project as required by the specific guidance at national / regional level (e.g. for detailed monitoring purposes)
- **Additional comments**: free text field which can be used by the editor e.g. for listing facilitating elements or obstacles for the implementation of the produced results, for suggestions for future actions/research, for messages to consumers, etc.

Context:

Rural Development Policy 2014-2020 and the European Union Research and Innovation Policy "Horizon 2020" both aim at demand-driven innovation and complement each other in providing opportunities for EIP interactive innovation projects. Rural development programmes are applied within a specific programme region, whilst H2020 research goes beyond this scale by funding innovative actions at transnational level. Rural development Operational Groups and interactive and practice-oriented projects under Horizon 2020, such as multi-actor projects and thematic networks, will feed the EIP-AGRI web database for practitioners using the common format.

Under the EIP-AGRI, synergies and complementarities have been developed between the Horizon 2020 EU research policy and the rural development policy under the CAP. Therefore, they all use the same EIP-AGRI web database. Moreover, all Horizon 2020 multi-actor projects are strongly recommended to involve relevant interactive innovation groups operating in the EIP-AGRI context, such as rural development Operational Groups. Multi-actor projects may provide potential innovative material to rural development Operational Groups for further development and vice versa. The EIP-AGRI network is there to link them.

Why an EIP-AGRI common format?

Communicating about projects, activities and results - both during and after the project's lifetime – at the EU level is much easier through the use of a common format for practice-oriented projects. Such common format **facilitates the knowledge flow and enables contacting** of farmers, researchers and all other actors involved in innovation projects. The content of the common format was developed and agreed at EU level thanks to the work of the Standing Committee for Agricultural Research (SCAR)^[2]. Using the common format for practice oriented projects will also give visibility to actors involved and enable measuring impact and rewarding of researchers' work for practice, in an analogue approach to research abstracts in peer reviewed journals.

How will the information in the EIP common format be shared?

The **EIP-AGRI website**^[3] will host and share the information at the EU level.. The EIP-AGRI common format is recommended to all projects that wish to provide information on their concrete outcomes for practitioners. These include interactive and practice-oriented innovation projects funded by sources other than rural development programmes and Horizon 2020, for instance national/ regional funding, Interreg, etc.

Which projects will use the common format?

The common element between the 3 types of projects listed below in more detail is that they all envisage implementing the EIP-AGRI interactive innovation approach, and all deliver outputs that are expected to be useful for practitioners.

1. Multi-actor projects

The H2020 **multi-actor approach**^[4] aims at demand-driven innovation: research projects' objectives and planning are targeted to needs/problems and opportunities of end-users, and should result in practical knowledge which is easy understandable and accessible. The approach requires that end-users and multipliers of research results, such as farmers, farmers' groups or advisors are closely involved throughout the whole project period. This should lead to innovative solutions that are more likely to be applied in the field, because those who need the solutions will be involved right from the start and will bring in complementary practical knowledge: from defining the questions, to planning, to implementing research work, to experiment and right up until possible demonstration and dissemination.

2. Thematic networks

Thematic networks^[5] are a particular format of multi-actor projects that aims to compile knowledge ready for practice in a specific field. This knowledge should be easily understandable for practitioners, stay available beyond the project period, and also be shared through the EIP-AGRI network. Thematic networks will summarise and present best practices and research results with a focus on themes and issues that are "near to be put into practice", but not sufficiently known yet by practitioners.

3. EIP Operational Groups

Operational Groups^[6] are multi-actor projects funded under the rural development policy. They have an obligation to make the plans and results of their work available for others in the EIP network to use. The use of the EIP-AGRI common format for reporting on operational group projects through the EIP-AGRI network will definitely play an important role in this regard, as it will help connecting Operational Groups funded under rural development with Horizon 2020 research consortia on specific topics and themes.

What are common elements for the "interactive" innovation projects developed under the EIP-AGRI?

In the **interactive innovation model**, building blocks for innovation are expected to come from science, but also from practice and intermediaries, such as farmers, advisors, businesses, NGOs, etc. Key for interactive innovation is to include existing (sometimes tacit) knowledge into building innovative solutions, which is crucial for tackling complex challenges in a holistic approach. In interactive innovation projects, end-users and practitioners are involved, not as a study-object, but in view of using their entrepreneurial skills and practical knowledge for developing the solution or opportunity and creating co-ownership. Innovation generated with an interactive approach tends to deliver solutions that are well adapted to real circumstances and easier to implement since the wider participation speeds up the acceptance and dissemination of new ideas. In short, the focus of interactive innovation is: "an idea put into practice with success". A new idea turns into a genuine innovation only if it is widely adopted and proves its usefulness in practice.

EIP-AGRI: "Ideas, put into practice, with success"

Having potential innovative knowledge is one thing, turning it into reality is another.

[1] The European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) was launched by the European Commission in 2012. It aims to foster a competitive and sustainable agriculture and forestry sector that "achieves more from less": <http://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/eip-agri-part-eu%E2%80%99s-growth-strategy-decade>

[2] The SCAR Strategic Working Group on Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (SWG AKIS) developed the common format on the basis of experience in Member States

[3] <http://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/>

[4] http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2016_2017/main/h2020-wp1617-food_en.pdf p.10 definition of multi-actor approach

[5] http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2016_2017/main/h2020-wp1617-food_en.pdf p.139 Thematic Networks compiling knowledge ready for practice

[6] See section 4.1 of the rural development EIP guidelines http://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/agri-eip/files/pb_guidelines_eip_implementation_2014_en.pdf

Instructions for the completion and submission of the 'EIP-AGRI common format' (Jan 2019)

This section provides information on how to use and complete the 'EIP-AGRI common format' Excel template. For general information and requirements on the common format, please refer to the official EC guidelines (see first sheet of this Excel document).

Note for Horizon 2020 project coordinators : please submit only one Excel file per project, including for following updates. In case of updates, ensure that you use the same project ID (see further below). Please send your completed Excel file to the following email address: AGRI-EIP-PRACTICE-ABSTRACTS@ec.europa.eu including your Project officer (REA) and Policy officer (DG AGRI) in copy of the message.

All obligatory, recommended and optional elements requested in the official guidelines can be recorded through this template.

The template is composed of different sections. Here below you can find a correlation table indicating which information required by the official guidelines is to be provided under each section of the Excel template. Under the section '**IDENTIFICATION**' you are asked to indicate whether the information refers to a **multi-actor project** or a **thematic network**.

Required information (in the sequence as foreseen in the official RD guidelines on the EIP-AGRI common format)	Section of the Excel template	Type of information
Title (native language)	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Title (in English)	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Editor	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Project coordinator	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Project partners	PARTNERS	Obligatory
Keyword-category	KEYWORDS	Obligatory
Project period	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Project status	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Funding source	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Total budget	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Main geographical location (NUTS3)	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Objective of the project (native language)	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Objective of the project (in English)	PROJECT INFORMATION	Obligatory
Short summary for practitioners (Practice abstract) in native language	PA1	Obligatory
Description of project activities (native language)	PROJECT INFORMATION	Recommended
Description of project activities (in English)	PROJECT INFORMATION	Recommended

Short summary for practitioners (Practice abstract) in English	PA	Recommended
Audiovisual material	AUDIOVISUAL	Recommended
Website	WEBSITES	Recommended
Links to other websites	WEBSITES	Recommended
Additional practice abstracts (native language)	PA2 to PA100	Optional
Additional practice abstracts (in English)	PA2 to PA100	Optional
Description of the context	PROJECT INFORMATION	Optional
Additional information	PROJECT INFORMATION	Optional
Additional comments	PROJECT INFORMATION	Optional

Who should complete the EIP-AGRI Common format and when?

The common format allows to provide information **all along the life-cycle of the project**, so its content can be updated at any moment when useful. It is recommended that the information on the project is made available as soon as possible **at the beginning of the project** in order to facilitate contacts (including with EIP Operational Groups) and that it is kept regularly updated.

It is expected that updates are transmitted as soon as new project results are available in the form of 'practice abstracts' (PA). Please do not submit multiple Excel files for the same project. The Excel template allows for recording and submitting up to **100** practice abstracts. Every time new practice abstracts are available you can add them to the same project file and submit an update. Please remember to include the project's unique ID.

All the project partners are expected to contribute to the submission of practice abstracts.
N.B.: The project coordinator remains responsible for the transmission of the EIP-AGRI common format and its updates.

PROJECT IDENTIFIER

It is very important that each Excel file (= each project) includes an unique ID number. This is particularly relevant in case of further updates.

The project identifier (ID) needs to be included in the relevant field as indicated in the work sheet named 'PROJECT INFORMATION' according the following rules/format:

[YYYY]H2020_[PROJECT ID NUMBER]_[PROJECT ACRONYM]

where:

YYYY = Start year of the project

Examples:

2015H2020_652642_AGRISPIN

2015H2020_652601_WINETWORK

2016H2020_678024_Strength2Food

Etc.

Printing instructions

To print one or more worksheets of this Excel template: click on '*Print*' under the menu '*File*' (or Ctrl + P) and then select the appropriate option under '*Settings*'

To save a **PDF version** of the Common format: 1) Select the worksheets you want to save (keep 'Ctrl' clicked for multiple selection of worksheets); 2) go to '*File*' > '*Save as*' and select 'PDF' under the drop-down menu '*Save as type*'.

It is recommended to perform a spell-check before the printing or submission of the template

INFORMATION ON USE OF PERSONAL DATA COLLECTED VIA THIS TEMPLATE

The project information provided with this template - thus including the contact details of the project coordinator and the project partners when these are provided - will be made publicly available on the EIP-AGRI website (<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en>). Visitors of the EIP-AGRI website may use this information to establish contacts with the project to, for example, propose collaborations and expand their network.

By submitting this template to the email account AGRI-EIP-PRACTICE-ABSTRACTS@ec.europa.eu the project coordinator and the project partners listed in the template are aware that the information provided in the template (including contact details when these are indicated) will be published on the EIP-AGRI website.

The acquisition of personal data through this template and their further processing are limited to the objectives and the operations described by the Privacy statement covering the activities of the EIP-AGRI Network, which is available at the following link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/privacy-statement-processing-personal-data-related>

In case you have questions related to the collection and processing of your personal data, the general rules for processing of personal information in the context of the EIP-AGRI network activity, or on your rights to have it modified, corrected or deleted, please contact agri-EIP@ec.europa.eu

Giving consensus for publishing contact details of the project coordinator and partners

Under the sections PROJECT INFORMATION and PARTNERS of this template, project coordinators and their partners are asked to provide their contact details and express their agreement to publish them on the EIP-AGRI website. The consent for publication is given by ticking the related consensus checkbox next to each partner's name.

ATTENTION: The project information provided with this template will be published on the EIP-AGRI website only if consensus for the publication of the contact details is provided through the procedure described above.

Project identification

Please indicate whether the information refers to a multi-actor project or a thematic network

Multi-actor project

Mandatory

Project Information

Project identifier (see INSTRUCTIONS) 101084084

Title of the project in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise repeat the title in English) Estrategias agroecológicas para la gestión sostenible de la maleza en cultivos Europeos clave

Title of the project in English (provide the project ACRONYM + short title within the characters limit) AGROSUS (Agroecological strategies for sustainable weed management in key European crops)

Geographical location

Country (of the coordinator) ES

Main geographical location (NUTS3) (of coordinator - for geolocalisation on map) ES114 - Pontevedra

Editor of the text: person/organisation responsible for delivering the text FEUGA

Project coordinator (lead-partner) according to the cooperation/consortium agreement:

Name	Adela María Sánchez Moreiras
Address	Departamento de Biología Vexetal e Ciencia do Solo, Facultade de Biología, Vigo, 36310, Spain
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Project period:

start year (YYYY)	2023
end year (YYYY)	2027

Project status: ongoing (after selection of the project) or completed (after final payment) ongoing

Main funding source (Rural development programme, H2020, or other EU, national/regional or private funds) H2020

Total budget of the project (total costs - in euros) € 4 689 926,25

Objective of the project in English: what problems/opportunities does the project address that are relevant for the practitioner/end-user, and how will they be solved? - (300-600 characters, word count – no spaces)

AGROSUS will identify tools and agroecological strategies (AS) to prevent and manage weeds in relevant crops, in conventional, organic, and mixed farming, across 11 biogeographic regions (Alpine, Anatolian, Arctic, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Macaronesian, Mediterranean, Pannonian and Steppic) of the EU and associated countries, aiming to reduce reliance on synthetic herbicides and the correlated pressure on the environment. AGROSUS will co-develop these tools and strategies with stakeholders, and the short, medium, and long-term impact of the agroecological strategies will be analysed from environmental and socio-economic perspectives.

Objective of the project in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise indicate "see objectives in English") (300-600 characters, word count – no spaces)

AGROSUS identificará herramientas y estrategias agroecológicas (EA) para prevenir y gestionar malezas en cultivos relevantes, en sistemas de cultivo convencional, orgánico y mixto, en las 11 regiones biogeográficas (Alpina, Anatolia, Ártica, Atlántica, Mar Negro, Boreal, Continental, Macaronesia, Mediterránea, Panónica y Estépica) en la UE y países asociados, con el objetivo de reducir la dependencia de herbicidas sintéticos y la presión sobre el medio ambiente. AGROSUS co-desarrollará estas herramientas y estrategias con las partes interesadas, y se analizará el impacto a corto, medio y largo plazo de las estrategias agroecológicas desde perspectivas ambientales y socioeconómicas

Description of project activities in English: (max 600 characters, word count – no spaces): short summary highlighting main project activities.

AGROSUS will provide crop management tools implementing techniques that allow sustainable, fair, and safe weed management in conventional, organic, and mixed farming systems, as well as fostering farmers' acceptance. Specific objectives: (1) establishment of cultural, mechanical, physical, biological, and biotechnological Agroecological System. (2) Technology transfer and training for the prevention and management of weeds. (3) Promote the most appropriate initiatives at the field, administration and regulatory levels. (4) Advanced detection tools. (5) Expand knowledge on problematic weeds on European Agriculture.

Description of project activities in native language: (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners) (can be (max 600 characters, word count – no spaces): short summary highlighting main project activities.

AGROSUS proporcionará herramientas de manejo implementando técnicas que permitan la gestión sostenible, justo y seguro de malezas en sistemas agrícolas convencionales, orgánicos y mixtos, así como fomentar la aceptación de los agricultores. Objetivos específicos: 1) Establecimiento del Sistema Agroecológico cultural, mecánico, físico, biológico y biotecnológico 2) Transferencia de tecnología y formación para la prevención y gestión de malas hierbas 3) Impulsar las iniciativas más adecuadas a nivel de campo, de administración y regulatorio 4) Herramientas de detección avanzadas 5) Expandir conocimientos sobre la problemática de las malezas en la Agricultura Europea

Description of the context of the project in English (e.g. drivers in legislation/ markets or other causes that were at the origin of the project, etc.)

Industrial large-scale crop monocultures dominate European agriculture, with low ecological diversity and high vulnerability to weed proliferation. This crop system involves the excessive use of synthetic herbicides. Despite its effectiveness, the overuse of synthetic herbicides has led to soil, air, and water pollution, as well as increased resistance in weed biotypes. In addition, climate change aggravates the situation by altering weed biology, reducing herbicide efficacy, and impacting crop-weed dynamics. Since 1991, EU policies have restricted 60% of pesticide substances, leaving farmers with limited alternatives and high dependency on synthetic herbicides, especially in economically key crops. However, this dependence conflicts with EU aims for sustainable agriculture, biodiversity preservation, and climate resilience. Agroecology based practices provide viable alternative by integrating ecological principles to enhance resilience, efficiency, and biodiversity. Agroecology emphasizes sustainable weed management through reduced herbicide use, alternative techniques, and increased farmer knowledge of the ecological benefits of weeds. By promoting local adaptation and co-creation with stakeholders, agroecology aligns with EU goals to ensure food security while addressing environmental challenges.

Additional information on the project in English (as appropriate e.g. about activities to connect with the relevant sector and actors, farmers, businesses, etc.)

Main results: -Stakeholder network actively participating in the decision and adoption of the agroecological strategies. - Reports on weed-associated problems, including an updated list of the most problematic weeds in Europe and factors hindering agroecological approaches adoption. -Guidelines about best agroecological approaches per crop and region through Europe. - Demonstrative videos of robots and drones' potential for early weed detection targeted to farmers and advisors. - Reports on agroecological approaches agronomic potential and delivery of ecosystem services. - Reports on agroecological approaches environmental and socio-economic impact. - Stakeholder's recommendations for agroecological approaches implementation in European agriculture. - Network with stakeholders to foster affiliated entities acceptance through identification, discussion, and eventual policy changes to favour agroecological approaches.

Additional comments (in English): free text field which can be used by the editor e.g. for listing facilitating elements or obstacles for the implementation of the produced results, for suggestions for future actions/research, for messages to end-users etc.

Project partners (mandatory information) - N.B. : "Name" can be that of the Organisation or of a contact person - "Address" should include the country

	Name	Address	E-mail	Telephone	Type of partner
project coordinator (lead partner) from PROJECT INFORMATION	Adela María Sánchez Moreir	Departamento de Biología Vexet	adela@uvigo.gal	+34 986818714	research institute
project partner	UVIGO	Departamento de Biología Vexet	adela@uvigo.gal , davidfc@uvigo.gal		other
project partner	CSIC	Calle Serrano 117, Madrid 28004	pablo.gonzalez@csic.es ; luis.emmi@car.upm-csic.es ; r		research institute
project partner	FEUGA	Rúa Lope Gómez de Marzoa, Ca	trodriguez@feuga.es		NGO
project partner	PNU	7 Staryi Boulevard, Zhytomyr 10	tanyavasiluk2015@gmail.com		other
project partner	UAK	Al Mickiewicza 21, Krakow 31 12	agnieszka.synowiec@urk.edu.pl ; marta.czekaj@urk.edu		other
project partner	UMA	Praça do Municipio, Funchal 900	miguel.carvalho@staff.uma.pt		other
project partner	UNIMI	Via Festa Del Perdono 7, Milano	fabrizio.araniti@unimi.it		other
project partner	SEIPASA	Ctra Almudevar 2, Tardienta Hud	ltorres@seipasa.com ; fchornet@seipasa.com		SME
project partner	MTU	Malatya Turgut Ozal, Universites	ibrahim.yanardag@ozal.edu.tr		other

Keyword - category

Keyword - category 1	Agricultural production system
Keyword - category 2	Farming practice
Keyword - category 3	Farming equipment and machinery
Keyword - category 4	Plant production and horticulture
Keyword - category 5	Climate and climate change
Keyword - category 6	
Keyword - category 7	
Keyword - category 8	
Keyword - category 9	
Keyword - category 10	

Audiovisual material which is useful and attractive for practitioners (e.g. YouTube link, videos, other dissemination material)

Recommended

Title/description (in English)	URL	Additional comments
	http://	

Official website of the project

Recommended

Title/description	URL	Additional comments
	http://	

Links to other website(s) hosting information on the project (results) that are available after the project has ended, by preference using the existing local/regional/national communication channels that practitioners most often use.

Recommended

Title/description	URL	Additional comments
	http://	

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Arctic region (Iceland)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most effective agroecological strategies for weed management in arable crops in the Arctic region? **STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS:** Crop rotation (86%) and tillage (75%) were the most common agroecological strategies used by farmers. Over 40% of farmers also used high planting densities and qualitative seed material. Methods like soil covers and flame weeding had only been heard of but never used. Only 17% of farmers knew about weed maps, with 75% having heard of hand weeding, and 62% of cover cropping and mulching. Other stakeholders were more familiar with crop rotation, competitive cultivars, cover crops, inter-row cultivation, and mixed cropping. However, only 22% knew about weed maps. Special planting dates, seed quality, and narrow rows were known to 67%, while methods like mowing, grazing, and soil covers were familiar to 78%. During a co-creation workshop, crop rotation, especially between grains and perennial grasses, was highlighted as vital for weed suppression and soil nutrient management in Iceland. Tillage is useful, but the most effective equipment differs between soil types. Precision agriculture, robots, and undersowing cover crops were of interest, but variable weather remained a challenge. **RECOMMENDATION:** Crop rotation should remain central to weed management, especially in grains and potatoes. Testing different fertilizers, sowing densities, and mechanical hilling methods could improve weed control. Precision agriculture and robotic weeding should be explored to reduce herbicide use.

Short title in native language

Hugmyndir hagsmunaaðila um algengustu landbúnaðarvistfræðilegu

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

ÁSKORUN: Hvaða aðferðir eru árangursríkastar við illgresiseyðingu í akuryrkju á norðurslóðum? ÁLIT HAGSMUNAAÐILA: Skiptiræktun (86%) og jarðvinnsla (75%) eru algengustu landbúnaðarvístfræðilegu aðferðirnar sem bændur nota. Yfir 40% nota einnig þéttari útplöntun og gæðafræ/útsæði. Allir bændurnir höfðu heyrt um jarðvegsdúka og illgresisbruna en höfðu þó ekki prófað þær aðferðir. Aðeins 17% bændanna þekktu til illgresiskorta, 75% höfðu heyrt um að reyta illgresi með höndunum og 62% um þekjurtir (cover crop) og þekjuefni (mulch). Aðrir hagsmunaaðilar í landbúnaði og garðyrkju þekktu einnig flestir til skiptiræktunar, þekjurturta, jarðvinnslu á milli raða eða rása og samplöntunar (e. intercropping). Hins vegar höfðu aðeins 22% heyrt um illgresiskort. Flestir (78%) þekktu til sláttar, beitar og jarðvegsdúka og 67% könnuðust við sérstaka dagsetningu sáningar, gæðafræ/útsæði og þéttari sáningu/útplöntun. Á vinnustofu var rætt um skiptiræktun og að sáðskipti milli korntegunda og grass væru nauðsynleg til þess að koma í veg fyrir útbreiðslu illgresis og til að bæta næringarefnabúskap jarðvegs. Einnig kom fram að jarðvinnsla getur verið áhrifarík aðferð en hvaða tæki henta best er mismunandi eftir jarðvegsgerðum. Áhugi er á nákvæmnisbúskap, notkun róbóta og skjólsáningu en rýsjótt veðurfar getur valdið erfiðleikum. RÁÐLEGGINGAR: Skiptiræktun ætti áfram að vera undirstaðan í aðgerðum gegn illgresi í ræktun á korni og kartöflum. Prófanir á mismunandi tegundum áburðar, þéttleika sáningar og hreykingu geta hugsanlega stuðlað að bættri illgresiseyðingu. Til þess að minnka notkun illgresiseyða ætti að kanna möguleikana sem felast í nákvæmnisbúskap og notkun róbóta við illgresiseyðingu.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 2:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological methods of weed control in the Arctic region (Iceland)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most effective agroecological strategies for weed management in horticultural crops in the Arctic region?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS: Arctic farmers rely on crop rotation and tillage for managing weeds. Stakeholders were also familiar with cover crops and mechanical cultivation, while 88% knew about intercropping. Weed flaming, living mulch, and agroecological service crops were known to 75%, though only 13% had heard of roller-crimpers. In the discussion group, crop rotation was highlighted as the most important weed management strategy, but land scarcity limits its effective use. Tillage remains essential, though no-till approaches tend to increase weed pressure. Weed burning, particularly in organic carrot farming, was used to a limited extent, using homemade burners. Other strategies like mechanical weeding, row tillers, robots, and soil covers were discussed. However, the short growing season makes it difficult to grow cover crops after harvest. Weed burning was also explored as a potential solution for controlling weeds. **RECOMMENDATION:** Crop rotation and mechanical weeding should be prioritized for weed management. Trials of mechanical weed control should be conducted across different regions to reduce herbicide use. Precision agriculture technologies, such as GPS and robotics, should be explored to improve sustainability. Despite challenges with cover crops, they should be considered for regions with longer growing periods or early-harvest crops.

Short title in native language

Hugmyndir hagsmunaaðila um algengustu landbúnaðarvistfræðilegu

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

ÁSKORUN: Hvaða aðferðir eru árangursríkastar við illgresiseyðingu í útiræktuðu grænmeti á norðurslóðum? ÁLIT HAGSMUNAAÐILA: Bændur á norðurslóðum reiða sig aðallega á skiptiræktun og jarðvinnslu í baráttunni við illgresi. Hagsmunaaðilar þekktu einnig til þekjurturta (cover crops) og illgresiseyðingar með vélum og 88% könnuðust við samplöntun (intercropping). Einnig þekktu 75% til illgresisbruna, skjólsáningar og plantna sem nýtast vistkerfinu. Aðeins 13% höfðu heyrt um valtara sem krumpar þekjurtirtir (roller-crimper). Í umræðuhópnum var rætt um að skiptiræktun væri mikilvægasta aðgerðin gegn illgresi en að landnáði væri oft ekki nægilegt til þess að bændur gætu nýtt sér aðferðina að fullu. Jarðvinnsla er mikilvæg og aðferðir við ræktun án jarðvinnslu (no-till) geta valdið auknu illgresisálagi. Illgresisbruni hefur verið notaður að einhverju leyti í lífrænni ræktun á gulrótum og þá með heimasmíðuðum búnaði. Einnig var rætt um illgresiseyðingu með tækjum, herfi, róbótum og jarðvegsdúkum. Stutt vaxtartímabil veldur því að erfitt er að rækta þekjurtirtir eftir uppskerutíma. Einnig var rætt um illgresisbruna sem mögulega lausn á illgresisvandamálum. RÁÐLEGGINGAR: Mesta áherslu ætti að leggja á skiptiræktun og illgresiseyðingu með tækjum. Til þess að minnka notkun illgresiseyða ætti að gera prófanir á tækjum fyrir illgresiseyðingu við mismunandi skilyrði. Einnig ætti að skoða notkun tæknilausna eins og GPS og róbóta til þess að stuðla að aukinni sjálfbærni. Þrátt fyrir að ræktun þekjurturta sé vandasöm ætti að íhuga notkun þeirra á svæðum með lengri vaxtartímabil eða þar sem ræktaðar eru tegundir sem hægt er að uppskera snemma.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 3:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control associated to arable crops in Atlantic region (Vigo, Spain)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) **outcomes** (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most popular agroecological methods for weed control in arable crops in the Atlantic region? **STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS:** In wheat and potato cultivation, crop rotation is the most common method for weed management (79%) used by farmers and know but all community, followed by tillage (70%), inter-row cultivation (62%) and quality seed-material. Although less frequently used high plant densities, mowing and grazing (15%) are also implemented. The least used practices include cover crops/mulches (11%), special planting dates (9%), narrow rows (6%), mixed cropping (2%), and weed maps (2%). A significant number of farmers (81%) were unaware of soil cover and flame weeding, highlighting a gap in knowledge. Participants reinforced the importance of crop rotation, while also suggesting bioherbicides, mechanical tillage, high seed density, and competitive cultivars for wheat. For potato, recommended strategies include low tillage, plowing, ridging, biofortifiers, and false seeding. **RECOMMENDATION:** An integrated approach combining crop rotation, mechanical tillage, and qualitative seed material is recommended for effective weed management in arable crops. Additionally, introducing bioherbicides, biofortifiers, and optimizing planting dates can further enhance control. Training programs should focus on less-known practices like soil cover, flame weeding, and mixed cropping to increase their adoption and effectiveness in sustainable farming systems.

Short title in native language

Coñecemento das partes interesadas sobre métodos agroecolóxicos de

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEMA: Cales son os métodos agroecolóxicos máis populares para o control de malas herbas nos cultivos de secaño da rexión atlántica? **VALORACIÓN DOS GRUPOS IMPLICADOS:** No cultivo de trigo e pataca, a rotación de cultivos é o método máis utilizado e coñecido (79%) para o control das malas herbas. Séguenlle a labranza (70%), o cultivo en fileiras (62%) e o uso de sementes de calidade. Aínda que se utilizan con menor frecuencia, a alta densidade de sementeira, a sega e o pastoreo (15%) tamén están presentes. As prácticas menos empregadas son os cultivos de cobertura (11%), data de sementeira especial (9%), fileiras estreitas (6%), cultivos mixtos (2%), e o mapeo de malas herbas (2%). O 81% dos participantes non coñecía o uso de cubertas do solo e a queima, o que pon de manifesto unha falta de coñecemento nestos métodos. Os participantes subliñaron a importancia da rotación de cultivos e suxeriron o uso de bioherbicidas, labranza mecánica, alta densidade de sementeira e variedades competitivas para o trigo. No caso da pataca, as estratexias recomendadas inclúen mínima labranza, arado, surcado, biofortificadores e falsa siembra. **RECOMENDACIÓN:** Recoméndase un enfoque integrado que combine rotación de cultivos, laboreo mecánico e material de sementeira de calidade para un control efectivo das malas herbas nos cultivos arables. Ademais, a introducción de bioherbicidas, biofortificadores e a optimización das datas de sementeira poden mellorar aínda máis o control de malas herbas. Os programas de capacitación deberían centrarse en prácticas menos coñecidas como a cobertura do solo, a queima e os cultivos mixtos para aumentar a súa adopción e efectividade en sistemas agrícolas sostibles.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 4:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Atlantic region (Vigo, Spain)

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

PROBLEM: What are the most commonly used agroecological methods for weed control in vineyards in the Atlantic region? **STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS:** Among surveyed farmers, stakeholders, and co-creation workshop participants, mowing is the most frequently used method for weed control in vineyards (82%), followed by tillage (68%) and spontaneous cover (42%). Inert mulching, living mulching, and both permanent and temporary cover crops are applied by 32% of respondents. Mechanical weed management and hand weeding are also well-known and practiced. Grazing, bioherbicides, and thermal weed control are much less common (5%). Despite this, these techniques, along with mixed cropping and cover crops with various species, were recommended in workshops as valuable options for enhancing agroecological weed control. Some stakeholders suggested the potential of bioherbicides and thermal weed control, but these remain underutilized. There is a strong interest in integrating diverse practices, such as spontaneous weed cover within rows and cover cropping between rows, to manage weeds effectively. However, lack of knowledge and practical training on these strategies remains a barrier to wider adoption. **RECOMMENDATION:** A combined approach utilizing mowing, diverse cover crops, and mulching is recommended for effective weed management in vineyards. Training and awareness programs should focus on underutilized methods such as bioherbicides and thermal weed control to improve adoption. Emphasizing these practices can enhance weed control, improve soil health, and contribute to more sustainable vineyard management in the Atlantic region.

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Short title in native language

Percepción dos participantes sobre os métodos agrocolóxicos máis

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEMA: Cales son os métodos agrocolóxicos máis utilizados para o control de malas herbas nos viñedos da rexión atlántica?

VALORACIÓN DOS GRUPOS IMPLICADOS: Entre os participantes, a sega é o método máis común para o control de malas herbas en viñedos (82%), seguido da labranza (68%) e la cobertura espontánea (42%). A cobertura inerte, a cobertura viva, e los cultivos de cobertura permanentes e temporais son aplicados polo 32% dos enquisados. A xestión mecánica das malas herbas e desherbado manual tamén son prácticas coñecidas. O pastoreo, os bioherbicidas e o control térmico son menos comúns (5%), pero se valoraron como opcións valiosas xunto cós cultivos mixtos. Algúns actores sinalaron o potencial dos bioherbicidas e o control térmico, aínda que seguen infrautilizados. Existe un interese crecente por integrar prácticas diversas, como a cobertura espontánea de malas herbas e cultivos de cobertura. Sen embargo, a falta de coñecemento e formación sobre estas estratexias é unha barreira para a súa adopción. **RECOMENDACIÓN:** Suxírese un enfoque combinado de sega, cultivos de cobertura e mulching para un manexo efectivo das malas herbas nos viñedos. Os programas de formación deberían centrarse en métodos pouco utilizados, como os bioherbicidas e o control térmico, para mellorar a súa adopción e contribuir a unha xestión máis sostible na rexión atlántica.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 5:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Boreal region (Estonia)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most effective agroecological methods for weed control in the boreal region? **STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS:** According to farmer surveys, crop rotation is the most widely used method, with 96% of respondents employing it. High-quality seed material is also prevalent, used by 83% of farmers, followed by mechanical tillage at 76%. Methods such as soil cover and flame weeding are less common, with only 19% of farmers having heard of them and 74% not utilizing them. Weed maps are notably underused, with just 18% of respondents employing them. Stakeholders and co-creation workshop participants agree on the importance of crop rotation, cover crops, and mechanical cultivation. Mowing is particularly emphasized for effective weed control in orchards. **RECOMMENDATION:** Implement crop rotation and use of certified seed material as core strategies for managing weeds. Mechanical cultivation should be employed widely, particularly in combination with cover crops to enhance soil health and weed suppression. Incorporate mowing in orchards to manage weed growth and maintain orchard health. Address practical challenges associated with soil cover and flame weeding by exploring financial incentives and technological advancements. Increase awareness and application of weed maps and bioherbicides to expand their use and effectiveness. Ensuring that these methods are tailored to local conditions will optimize their impact on sustainable agricultural practices.

Short title in native language

Huvirühmade arvamused kõige sagedamini kasutatavast

Short summary for practitioners in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEEM: Millised on kõige tõhusamad agroökoloogilised meetodid umbrohutõrjeks boreaalses piirkonnas?

SIDUSRÜHMADE ARVAMUSED: Põllumajandustootjate küsitluste kohaselt on külvikord kõige laialdasemalt kasutatav meetod, mida rakendab 96% vastanutest. Kvaliteetset seemnematerjali kasutab samuti suur osa tootjatest (83%), millele järgneb mehaaniline harimine (76%). Meetodid nagu mullapinna katmine ja umbrohu leegitamine on piirkonnas vähem levinud, nendest on kuulnud vaid 19% tootjatest ja 74% ei kasuta neid. Umbrohu kaarte kasutatakse märkimisväärselt vähe, vaid 18% vastanutest. Sidusrühmad ja kaasloome töötoa osalejad nõustuvad külvikorra, vahekultuuride ja mehaanilise harimise olulisuses. Niitmist tuuakse esile eriti tõhusa umbrohutõrje meetodina viljapuuaiades.

SOOVITUS: Rakendada külvikorda ja sertifitseeritud seemnematerjali kasutamist umbrohutõrje põhistrateegiatena. Mehaanilist harimist tuleks laialdaselt kasutada, eriti koos vahekultuuridega, et parandada mulla tervist ja umbrohutõrje efektiivsust. Viljapuuaiades tuleks umbrohtude allasurumiseks ja viljapuuai tervise säilitamiseks rakendada niitmist. Lahendada mulla katmise ja leegitamisega seotud praktilised väljakutsed, uurides rahalisi stiimuleid ja uudseid tehnoloogilisi võimalusi. Suurendada teadlikkust umbrohu kaartide ning bioherbitsiidide kohta, et laiendada nende kasutamist ja tõhusust. Nende meetodite kohalike tingimustega kohandamise tagamine optimeerib nende mõju säästvatele põllumajandustavadele.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 6:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in perennial crops in Boreal region (Estonia)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most effective agroecological strategies for weed management in perennial crops in the Boreal region?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS: Perennial farmers demonstrate a high level of awareness and adoption of agroecological practices for weed management. The most common methods include mowing (e.g., under tree canopies), organic and inorganic mulching, and planting cover crops. Mowing is well considered for controlling weeds and creating green mulch, which protects soil health. Farmers also noted that organic and inorganic mulches act as a barrier to light, reducing weed germination. Less familiar are bioherbicides and thermal weed control, which offer sustainable, non-chemical alternatives. Other stakeholders also highlighted grazing (by sheep and chickens) in organic orchards. Traditional methods (mowing, mulching) are preferred for ease and effectiveness, while newer techniques (thermal control) are more limited by the need of specialized equipment.
RECOMMENDATION: For Boreal perennial crops, an integrated approach is recommended, emphasising mowing, mulching, grazing and cover crops to sustainably manage weeds while improving soil health. Additionally, farmer training in less used and known methods (e.g., bioherbicides, thermal control), together with financial support, could further enhance the adoption of sustainable weed management practices.

Short title in native language

Sidusrühmade arusaamad kõige sagedamini kasutatavast

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEEM: Millised on kõige tõhusamad agroökoloogilised strateegiad umbrohutõrjeks mitmeaastastes kultuurides Boreaalpiirkonnas?
SIDUSRÜHMADE ARUSAAMAD: Põllumajandustootjad on väga teadlikud ja rakendavad aktiivselt agroökoloogilisi umbrohutõrje võtteid. Kõige levinumad meetodid hõlmavad niitmist (nt puuvõrade all), orgaanilist ja anorgaanilist multšimist ning kattekultuuride istutamist. Niitmist hinnatakse kõrgelt umbrohutõrje ja roheline multši loomise tõttu, mis kaitseb mulda. Põllumajandustootjad märkisid ka, et orgaanilised ja anorgaanilised multšid takistavad valguse jõudmist pinnasesse, vähendades umbrohtuseemnete idanemist. Vähem tuntud on bioherbitsiidid ja termiline umbrohutõrje, mis pakuvad jätkusuutlikke, keemiavabu alternatiive. Sidusrühmad töid esile ka karjatamise (nt lammaste ja kanade poolt) maheviljapuuaiades. Traditsioonilisi meetodeid (niitmine, multšimine) eelistatakse lihtsuse ja tõhususe tõttu, samas kui uuemad tehnikad (termiline tõrje) on piiratud spetsiaalse varustuse vajadusega.

SOOVITUS: Boreaalpiirkonna mitmeaastaste kultuuride jaoks soovitatakse integreeritud lähenemisviisi, mis rõhutab niitmist, multšimist, karjatamist ja kattekultuuride kasutamist umbrohtude jätkusuutlikuks tõrjeks ning mulla tervise parandamiseks. Lisaks võiksid põllumajandustootjad saada koolitust vähem tuntud meetodite (nt bioherbitsiidid, termiline tõrje) osas ning rahalist toetust, et edendada jätkusuutlike umbrohutõrjepraktikate laiemat kasutuselevõttu.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 7:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Continental region (Germany)

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

PROBLEM: What are the most popular and effective agroecological methods for weed control in the continental region (Germany)?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS: All stakeholders agreed on inter-row tillage, mechanical tillage, crop rotation, high seed rates and mulching. A significant group of stakeholders were familiar with other methods such as manual weed control (80%), certified seeds (80%), cover crops and mowing pastures (80%). Mechanical tillage was also the most frequently used method reported by farmers (50%), followed by crop rotation and certified seeds, each used by 40% of respondents. Other methods, such as tillage between rows, mixed cropping, increased seed rates, and cover crops, are utilized by only 10% of farmers. Methods like weed mapping and flaming, narrow rows, sowing timing and ground covers are less common due to lower awareness and high costs.
RECOMMENDATION: Emphasize the use of mechanical tillage, crop rotation, and certified seeds as primary strategies for weed control. Encourage the adoption of mulch and no-till seeding to improve soil health and weed management. Promote financial incentives for high-cost methods like flaming, especially in specialized crops. Increase awareness and training on lesser-known methods such as weed mapping and cover crops to enhance overall effectiveness in weed control.

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Short title in native language

Wahrnehmung der Stakeholder zur am häufigsten verwendeten

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: Was sind die beliebtesten und wirksamsten agrarökologischen Methoden zur Unkrautbekämpfung im kontinentalen Raum (Deutschland)? **WAHRNEHMUNGEN DER Stakeholder:** Alle Stakeholder waren sich über Reihenbodenbearbeitung, mechanische Bodenbearbeitung, Fruchtfolge, hohe Saatmengen und Mulchen einig. Eine bedeutende Gruppe von Interessenvertretern war mit anderen Methoden wie manueller Unkrautbekämpfung (80 %), zertifiziertem Saatgut (80 %), Zwischenfrüchten und dem Mulchen (80 %) vertraut. Auch die mechanische Bodenbearbeitung war nach Angaben der Landwirte die am häufigsten genutzte Methode (50 %), gefolgt von Fruchtfolge und zertifiziertem Saatgut, die jeweils von 40 % der Befragten genutzt wurden. Andere Methoden wie die Bodenbearbeitung zwischen den Reihen, Mischanbau, erhöhte Saatmengen und Zwischenfrüchte werden nur von 10 % der Landwirte genutzt. Methoden wie Unkrautkartierung und Abflammen, schmale Reihen, Saatzeitpunkt und Untersaat sind aufgrund geringerer Bekanntheit und hoher Kosten weniger verbreitet. **EMPFEHLUNG:** Sehen Sie den Einsatz mechanischer Bodenbearbeitung, Fruchtwechsel und zertifiziertes Saatgut als primäre Strategien zur Unkrautbekämpfung. Fördern Sie den Einsatz von Mulch- und Direktsaat, um die Bodengesundheit und die Unkrautbekämpfung zu verbessern. Schaffen Sie finanzielle Anreize für kostenintensive Methoden wie das Abflammen, insbesondere bei Sonderkulturen. Sensibilisierung und Schulung für weniger bekannte Methoden wie Unkrautkartierung und Zwischenfrüchte, um die allgemeine Wirksamkeit der Unkrautbekämpfung zu verbessern.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 8:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Continental region (Ukraine)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most popular and frequently used agroecological methods of weed control among farmers in the continental region of Ukraine? **STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS:** Among surveyed farmers, high-quality seed material is considered the most important agroecological method, with 96% of farmers using it. Crop rotation (92%), tillage (94%), competitive cultivars and high planting density are also widely practiced by farmers and workers. However, methods like inter-row cultivation and hand weeding have seen a decline, with 47% and 37% of farmers, respectively, no longer using them. Practices like soil cover and flame weeding (53%), as well as mowing and grazing (51%), are known but underutilized. Some farmers are unfamiliar with these methods, with 43% unaware of mowing and grazing and 35% unfamiliar with cover crops or mulches. Respondants emphasize the importance of certified seed material to avoid weed spread from self-produced seeds. Mechanical methods like plowing, disking, and harrowing are seen as effective, while biological methods using natural enemies of weeds show promise. Stakeholders agree that herbicides should be used minimally and precisely. **RECOMMENDATION:** A well-structured crop rotation system, including cereals and legumes and combined with mechanical tillage, is essential for effective weed management and soil health improvement. Research and training on the benefits of crop rotation, along with using certified seeds, should be prioritized to promote sustainable farming practices. Encourage community involvement in managing roadside weeds and explore biological methods to reduce reliance on herbicides.

Short title in native language

Сприйняття стейкхолдерами найчастіше застосовуваних

Short summary for practitioners in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

ПРОБЛЕМА: Які найбільш популярні та ефективні агроекологічні методи боротьби з бур'янами використовуються у континентальному регіоні України?

Серед опитаних фермерів найважливішим агроекологічним прийомом відмічався високоякісний насіннєвий матеріал (96% фермерів). Сівозміна (92%), обробіток ґрунту (94%), конкурентоспроможні сорти та ущільнені посіви також одні з найбільш застосовуваних практик. Менш поширені міжрядні обробітки та ручна прополка, відповідно 47% та 37% фермерів більше не використовують їх. Стейкхолдери знайомі з низкою практик, таких як покривні культури та вогнева прополка (53%), а також викошування та випас худоби (51%), однак недостатньо їх використовують. Деякі фермери (43%) не знайомі або не розуміють переваг вишування та випасу худоби, а 35% не знайомі з методами застосування покривних культур або мульчі. Респонденти підкреслили важливість сертифікованого насіннєвого матеріалу для запобігання поширенню бур'янів. Механічні методи (оранка, дискування тощо) вважаються ефективними, а біологічні методи є перспективними. Стейкхолдери погоджуються, що гербіциди повинні використовуватися у мінімальних кількостях і точково.

РЕКОМЕНДАЦІЯ: Оптимальна система сівозміни, яка включатиме зернові та бобові культури, у поєднанні з механічним обробітком, має важливе значення для ефективного управління бур'янами та поліпшення стану ґрунту. Дослідження та навчання щодо переваг сівозмін, використання сертифікованого насіння, повинні бути пріоритетними для просування стійкої сільськогосподарської практики. Важливим є заохочення участі громад в управлінні бур'янами на узбіччях доріг та вивчення біологічних методів боротьби з бур'янами для зменшення залежності від гербіцидів.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 9:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Macaronesian region (Madeira)

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

PROBLEM: What are the most popular and effective agroecological methods for weed control in Macaronesian region? **STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS:** Manual weeding is the most frequently used method, with 83% of custard apple producers and 80% of vine growers relying on it. Crop rotation is also widely practiced, with 66% of custard apple and 60% of vine producers adopting it. Physical and mechanical methods, such as mulching and green coverages, are emphasized in workshops as effective strategies. However, flame weeding is not utilized by any respondents. Tillage (mechanical cultivation) is known by 66% of custard apple and 80% of vine growers but is less commonly applied. In past practices, high planting densities are no longer used by 50% of custard apple and 60% of vine producers. Inter-row cultivation and mixed cropping are known but not widely adopted. Methods like soil cover and flame weeding are familiar to 63% of respondents but are rarely used. **RECOMMENDATION:** Manual weeding and crop rotation are the most reliable methods for weed control and should be prioritized. Integrating mulching and green coverages, along with promoting mechanical tillage, can enhance weed management. There is also a need to revisit and support the use of less common methods like soil cover and flame weeding through further research and farmer education to build a more comprehensive weed control strategy.

This summary should at least contain the following information:
– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
– The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Short title in native language

Percepções dos Agentes Interessados sobre os métodos

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEMA: Quais são os métodos agroecológicos mais populares e eficazes para o controlo de infestantes na região da Macaronésia?
PERCEPÇÕES DOS AGENTES INTERESSADOS: A monda manual é o método mais frequentemente utilizado, em que segundo os mesmos, 83% dos produtores de anona e 80% dos viticultores a recorrerem a este método. A rotação de culturas é também amplamente praticada, com 66% dos produtores de anona e 60% dos produtores de vinha a adotá-la. Os métodos físicos e mecânicos, como o mulching e as coberturas verdes, foram enfatizados nos seminários como sendo estratégias eficazes. No entanto, a monda à chama não é utilizada na região. A lavoura (cultivo mecânico) é conhecida por 66% dos produtores de anona e 80% dos produtores de vinha, mas é menos comumente aplicada. No que diz respeito às práticas anteriores, 50% dos produtores de anona e 60% dos produtores de vinha não utilizam densidades de plantação elevadas. A cultura entre fileiras e as culturas mistas são conhecidas, mas não são amplamente adotadas. Métodos como a cobertura do solo e a monda por chama são familiares a 63% dos inquiridos, mas raramente são utilizados. **RECOMENDAÇÃO:** A monda manual e a rotação de culturas são os métodos mais fiáveis para o controlo de ervas daninhas e devem ser priorizados. A integração de mulching e coberturas verdes, juntamente com a promoção da lavoura mecânica, pode melhorar a gestão das ervas daninhas. É também necessário rever e apoiar a utilização de métodos menos comuns, como a cobertura do solo e a monda à chama, através de mais investigação e da educação dos agricultores, para criar uma estratégia mais abrangente de controlo das infestantes.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 10:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in perennial crops in Mediterranean region (Valencia, Spain)

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most effective agroecological strategies for weed management in perennial crops in the Mediterranean region?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS: Mowing was the most frequently used method of weed control among farmers, with 42% using it regularly. Weed covers (26%), tillage (21%), and inert mulches (18%) were also common, while less frequently used methods included permanent and temporal cover crops (13%), grazing and bioherbicides (11%), and intercrops and living mulches (8% and 5%, respectively). Farmers had abandoned tillage (26%) and weed covers (16%) the most, with lesser discontinuation of living mulches (13%) and mowing (11%). Stakeholders familiar with perennial crops identified tillage (65.2%), temporal cover crops (62.1%), and mowing (62.1%) as the most familiar strategies. Weed covers (60.6%), inert mulches (57.6%), and permanent cover crops (57.6%) also had widespread awareness. Mechanical and thermal methods, bioherbicides and intercrops, were less known but still considered useful. Participants highlighted key strategies for the Mediterranean region, including preventive methods like crop rotation, cover crops, and organic and plastic mulching. Mechanical methods such as mowing were frequently mentioned, with drip irrigation identified as useful for water management and bioherbicides seen as an alternative to conventional herbicides. **RECOMMENDATION:** Focus on cover crops or managed spontaneous weed cover inter-row, and mulching or cover crops in the tree-line, as central weed management practices. Explore grazing, bioherbicides, and drip irrigation to enhance sustainability.

Short title in native language

Percepcions de les parts interessades sobre el mètode agroecològic

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEMA: Quines són les estratègies agroecològiques més efectives per a la gestió de males herbes en cultius perennes a la regió mediterrània? **PERCEPCIONS DELS PARTICIPANTS:** La sega era el mètode més utilitzat (42%). Les cobertes de males herbes (26%), el conreu de males herbes (21%) i els mulchings inerts (18%) eren habituals, i els menys utilitzats els cultius de cobertura permanents i temporals (13%), pasturatge i bioherbicides (11%) i conreus intercalats (8%) i mulchings vius (5%). Els agricultors havien abandonat el conreu de males herbes (26%), les cobertes de males herbes (16%), els mulchings vius (13%) i la sega (11%). Les parts interessades familiaritzades amb els cultius perennes van identificar el conreu de males herbes (65,2%), els cultius de cobertura temporal (62,1%) i la sega (62,1%) com les estratègies més conegudes. Les cobertes de males herbes (60,6%), les cobertures inerts (57,6%) i els cultius de cobertura permanents (57,6%) també van tenir una gran coneiximent. Els mètodes mecànics i tèrmics, els bioherbicides i els conreus intercalats, eren menys coneguts però es van considerar útils. Els participants van destacar la rotació de cultius, cultius de cobertura i mulching orgànic i plàstic. La sega es va esmentar amb freqüència, i el reg per degoteig va ser identificat com a útil per a la gestió de l'aigua. Els bioherbicides van ser considerats com una alternativa als herbicides convencionals. **RECOMANACIÓ:** Centrar-se en els cultius de cobertura o la coberta de males herbes espontànies manejades entre les fileres, i els cultius de cobertura o coberta a la línia d'arbres, com a pràctiques principals per a la gestió de males herbes. Explorar el pasturatge, els bioherbicides i el reg per degoteig per millorar la sostenibilitat.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 11:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in horticultural crops in Mediterranean region (Valencia, Spain)

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most effective agroecological strategies for weed management in horticultural crops in the Mediterranean region?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS: Among farmers, crop rotation and roller-crimper were the most common weed control methods (24%), followed by living mulch and cover crops (16%). Mechanical cultivation, agroecological service crops, and weed flaming were used by 11%, while intercropping and biological control were less common (8% and 5%). Some methods, like mechanical cultivation (24%) and intercropping (16%), were discontinued by many farmers. Biological weed control and weed flaming were known but not used by 21%, and 21% had never heard of agroecological service crops or biological control. Stakeholders familiar with horticultural practices recognized mechanical cultivation and crop rotation (53%) and were aware of biological control and weed flaming (51.5%). Roller-crimper, living mulch, and intercropping had moderate awareness (40-44%), but agroecological service crops were the least familiar (24%). Key strategies identified for Mediterranean weed management included preventive methods like crop rotation, cover crops, mulching, solarization, and false sowing, as well as mechanical methods like mowing. Drip irrigation was also highlighted for its role in reducing weed pressure. Bioherbicides were recommended as alternatives to conventional herbicides. **RECOMMENDATION:** Crop rotation, organic mulching with rice straw or biofilm should be prioritized. Testing living mulch and roller-crimper alongside bioherbicides and improved water management could further enhance weed control.

Short title in native language

Percepcions de les parts interessades sobre el mètode agroecològic

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEMA: Quines són les estratègies agroecològiques més efectives per a la gestió de males herbes en cultius hortícoles a la regió Mediterrània?

PERCEPCIONS DE LES PARTS INTERESSADES: la rotació de cultius i el rodet-engruixador (24%), els cultius vius i els cultius de cobertura (16%) eren les estratègies més utilitzades. El cultiu mecànic, els cultius de serveis agroecològics i el cremat van ser utilitzats en un 11%. Els conreus intercalats i el control biològic van ser menys freqüents (8% i 5%, respectivament). El cultiu mecànic (24%) i els cultius intercalats (16%), van ser interromputs per molts agricultors. El control biològic de males herbes i el cremat eren coneguts, però no els feien servir el 21%. El 21% mai havia sentit parlar de cultius de serveis agroecològics o de control biològic. Les parts interessades familiaritzades amb pràctiques hortícoles van reconèixer el cultiu mecànic i la rotació de cultius (53%) i eren conscients del control biològic i el cremat (52%). L'engruixadora de rodets, el mulching viu i els cultius intercalats tenien un coneixement moderat (40-44%). Els cultius de serveis agroecològics eren els menys coneguts (24%). Les estratègies clau identificades van ser preventives (rotació de cultius, cultius de cobertura, mulching, solarització i sembra falsa) i mecàniques, com la sega. Es va destacar el paper del reg per degoteig en la reducció de la pressió de les males herbes. Es va recomanar l'ús de bioherbicides com a alternatives als herbicides convencionals. **RECOMANACIÓ:** S'ha de prioritzar la rotació de cultius, el mulching amb palla d'arròs i el biofilm. Probar el mulching viu amb l'ús de corró-triturador, juntament amb bioherbicides i una millor gestió de l'aigua podrien millorar el control de les males herbes.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 12:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Mediterranean region (Cartagena, Spain)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most commonly used and recommended agroecological methods for weed control in Mediterranean almond and olive orchards? **STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS** In the surveyed group of farmers, tillage or mechanical cultivation is the most used method, applied by 81% of respondents, followed by live cover (70%) and weed cover (67%). In contrast, combined systems (11%), intercropping (8%), and grazing (4%) are the least used methods. No respondents have used inert mulches, bioherbicides, or thermal weed control. Historical data shows that mowing (15%) and intercropping (8%) were once used but are no longer practiced. Farmers have heard about but never used inert mulches (70%), grazing, intercropping, and bioherbicides (61%). Thermal weed control, bioherbicides, and grazing are the least known methods, unfamiliar to 42%, 38%, and 35% of respondents, respectively. In interviews, stakeholders overwhelmingly recognized mowing, inert mulches, living mulching, intercrops, and weed covers (90%). Mechanical cultivation, permanent cover crops, bioherbicides, and thermal weed control were also well known (80%). Temporal cover crops were the least known (74%). **RECOMMENDATION:** For sustainable weed management in Mediterranean almond and olive orchards, implement cover crops, mulching, weed covers, and intercropping. Emphasizing the inclusion of livestock could be a viable and economical addition. Expanding knowledge of bioherbicides and biotechnological methods is crucial for diversifying weed control strategies.

Short title in native language

Percepciones de los interesados sobre el método agroecológico más

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEMA: ¿Cuáles son los métodos agroecológicos más utilizados y recomendados para el control de malas hierbas en huertos mediterráneos de almendros y olivos? **PERCEPCIONES DE LOS INTERESADOS:** En el grupo de agricultores encuestados, la labranza o el control mecánico es el método más utilizado, aplicado por el 81% de los encuestados, seguido por cubiertas vivas (70%) y cubiertas de malas hierbas (67%). En contraste, los sistemas combinados (11%), el cultivo intercalado (8%) y el pastoreo (4%) son los métodos menos utilizados. Ninguno de los encuestados ha utilizado acolchados inertes no vivos, bioherbicidas o control térmico de malas hierbas aunque un 42%, 38% y 35% de los entrevistados conocen estos métodos respectivamente. Los datos históricos muestran que la siega (15%) y el cultivo intercalado (8%) se utilizaron en el pasado, pero ya no se practican. Las partes interesadas reconocieron en su gran mayoría la siega, los acolchados inertes, el acolchado vivo, los cultivos intercalados y las cubiertas de malas hierbas (90%). El control mecánico, los cultivos de cobertura permanentes, los bioherbicidas y el control térmico de malas hierbas también fueron bien conocidos (80%). Los cultivos de cobertura temporales fueron los menos conocidos (74%). **RECOMENDACIÓN:** Para una gestión sostenible de malas hierbas en huertos mediterráneos de almendros y olivos, se recomienda implementar cultivos de cobertura, acolchado, cubiertas de malas hierbas y cultivo intercalado. Hacer énfasis en la inclusión de ganado podría ser una opción viable y económica. Ampliar el conocimiento sobre bioherbicidas y métodos biotecnológicos es crucial para diversificar las estrategias de control de malas hierbas.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 13:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Pannonian region (Hungary)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most effective agroecological strategies for weed management in arable crops in the Pannon region?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS: Farmers use tillage, crop rotation, and quality seed as their primary agroecological techniques. Additional methods such as inter-row cultivation, mixed cropping, cover crops, high seeding density, mulching, and mowing are also commonly adopted due to their compatibility with conventional farming and direct benefits to farmers. Despite the presence of these techniques, chemical weed control remains the dominant practice, praised for its effectiveness and simplicity. However, stakeholders reported the need for developing bioherbicides to minimize environmental impacts. Mechanical weeding (inter-row cultivators), was frequently cited as an alternative, with no-till, min-till, cover crops, and mulching also recommended. Other practices could be pre-cropping with competitive plants, high-density planting, and utilizing competitive cultivars. Concerns were raised about the labor-intensive nature of certain methods and the long-term sustainability of reduced soil disturbance. Participants acknowledged that since chemical use secures yields, it cannot be completely abandoned. There is a recognized need for further research on mulch-free systems.
RECOMMENDATION: Testing of soil-friendly mechanical weeding methods and spray technologies that partially or completely eliminate herbicide use, as well as development of species-specific bioherbicides can reduce chemical dependence while promoting agroecological practices such as cover crops and competitive cultivars.

Short title in native language

Véleményfelmérés a Pannon régióban (Magyarországon) leggyakrabban

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

KÉRDÉS: Melyek a leghatékonyabb agroökológiai stratégiák a szántóföldi kultúrákban a Pannon régióban? **A VÁLASZADÓK VÉLEMÉNYE:** A gazdálkodók az agroökológiai módszerek közül elsősorban a szántást, a vetésforgót és a minőségi vetőmagot használják. A hagyományos gazdálkodással való kompatibilitásuk és a gazdálkodók számára közvetlen előnyök miatt a sorközművelést, a vegyes termesztést, a takarónövényeket, a nagy vetéssűrűséget, a talajtakarást és a kaszálást is alkalmazzák. Ugyanakkor továbbra is a vegyszeres gyomirtás az uralkodó gyakorlat, amelynek fő előnyei a hatékonyság és az egyszerű alkalmazás. A válaszadók azonban úgy vélték, hogy bioherbicidek fejlesztésére van szükség a környezeti hatások minimalizálása érdekében. Alternatívaként a mechanikus gyomlálást (sorközi kultivátorok), a no-till és min-till technikákat, a takarónövényeket és a talajtakarást is javasolták. Egyéb lehetőségek között szerepelt az elővetemény versenyképes növényekkel, a nagy sűrűségű ültetés és a versenyképes fajták hasznosítása. Aggályok merültek fel egyes módszerek munkaigényességével és a csökkent talajbolygatás hosszú távú fenntarthatóságával kapcsolatban. A résztvevők elismerték, hogy mivel a vegyszerhasználat biztosítja a hozamot, nem lehet teljesen elhagyni. Felismerték, hogy további kutatásokra van szükség a mulcsmentes rendszerekkel kapcsolatban. **AJÁNLÁS:** A herbicid használatot részben vagy egészen kiváltó talajbarát mechanikus gyomirtó módszerek és permetezési technológiák alkalmazása, valamint a fajspecifikus bioherbicidek fejlesztése csökkentheti a kémiai függőséget, miközben elősegíti az agroökológiai gyakorlatokat, például a takarónövények és a versenyképes fajták alkalmazását.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 14:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Pannonian region (Hungary)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most effective agroecological strategies for weed management in horticultural crops in the Pannon region?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS: Crop rotation followed by ploughing, stalk crushing, and ground cover crops are the most frequently used strategies. Most people are familiar with mechanical methods (like inter-row cultivation) and crop rotation. Chemical weed control is widespread, efficient, and well-supported by industry lobbying, while agroecological methods are appreciated for their ease of integration into conventional farming. Participants emphasized the potential of mulching and cover crops to improve weed management efficiency. To minimize soil contamination and preserve fertility, stakeholders recommended limiting chemical treatments to crop rows and using medium-depth soil loosening instead of ploughing. Applying herbicides only once after seeding, using quality seeds and relying on delayed cultivation were suggested to reduce chemical use. Practices such as no-till and min-till, have gained traction during last decade as can increase humus content and reduce soil disturbance. Respondants suggested using mulch, cover plants and allelopathic crops to suppress weeds. Additionally, creating more diverse systems mixed with trees, such as agroforestry, was proposed to improve soil biology, employment opportunities, and farmer income. **RECOMMENDATION:** Experiments should focus on mixed cropping systems, including agroforestry and medicinal herbs, combined with various soil covers to evaluate their weed-suppressing abilities. Reducing herbicide use through targeted application and mechanical methods, along with regenerative practices like no-till, should also be prioritized

Short title in native language

Véleményfelmérés a Pannon régióban (Magyarországon) leggyakrabban

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

KÉRDÉS: Melyek a leghatékonyabb agroökológiai stratégiák a kertészeti kultúrákban a Pannon régióban? **A VÁLASZADÓK VÉLEMÉNYE:** A vetésforgó, a szántás, a szárzúzás és a talajtakaró növények a leggyakrabban használt stratégiák. A vegyszeres gyomirtás széles körben elterjedt, hatékony és erős az ipari háttértámogatása, míg az agroökológiai módszereket a hagyományos gazdálkodásba való könnyű integrálhatóságuk miatt alkalmazzák. A résztvevők hangsúlyozták a talajtakarás, a takarónövények és az élő vagy inert mulcs használatát, mint a gyomirtás hatékonyságát javító módszereket. A talajszennyezés minimálisra csökkentése és a termékenység megőrzése érdekében a szakemberek és gazdálkodók javaslata a vegyszeres kezelés korlátozása a vetéssorokra, valamint szántás helyett közepes mélységű talajlazítás alkalmazása. A vegyszerhasználat csökkentése érdekében javasolták a gyomirtó szerek vetés utáni egyszeri kijuttatását, a minőségi magvak felhasználását és a kései vetést. A sekély talajművelés, min-till, no-till alkalmazása terjed, mivel növelhetik a humusztartalmat és csökkenthetik a talaj zavarását. A talajtakarás, takarónövények és allelopátiás növények használata is a javaslatok között szerepelt. Emellett a talajbiológia, a foglalkoztatási lehetőségek és a gazdálkodók jövedelmének javítása érdekében változatosabb, fákkal kevert rendszerek (agrárerdészet) kialakítását javasolták. **AJÁNLÁS:** A kísérleteknek a fákkal vegyes kultúrákra kell összpontosítaniuk, vizsgálva a különböző gyógynövények és talajtakarások gyomelnyomó hatékonyságát. Előtérbe kell helyezni a célzott kijuttatást és a mechanikai gyomirtást, valamint az olyan regenerációs gyakorlatokat, mint a közvetlen talajművelés.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 15:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Pannonian region (Hungary)

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most effective agroecological strategies for weed management in perennial crops in the Pannon region?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS: Mowing is the most commonly used weed control technique for perennial crops in the Pannon region. They also employ inert and living mulches, along with perennial ground cover plants. These methods are favored because they easily integrate into conventional farming and require minimal attention, providing direct benefits to farmers. Many stakeholders are familiar with seasonal cover crops, grazing, weeding, and ploughing, but most do not actively use these methods. Participants view mixed cropping, mulching, and cover crops as effective weed management strategies. However, the high cost of mulching limits its adoption. Additionally, stakeholders highlighted the need for soil-friendly mechanical weeding practices and improvements in machine design. The challenge of replacing herbicides is also significant, with calls for developing alternative chemicals that are less harmful to plants and ecosystems. **RECOMMENDATION:** Establish an experimental design with ecosystem-friendly practices usable in organic production such as mixed cropping (perennial crops in agroforestry intercropping) combined with inter-row weeding and use of effective bio-substances that trigger herbicides.

Short title in native language

Véleményfelmérés a Pannon régióban (Magyarországon) leggyakrabban

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

KÉRDÉS: Melyek a leghatékonyabb agroökológiai stratégiák a Pannon régió évelő kultúráinak gyomirtására? **A VÁLASZADÓK VÉLEMÉNYE:** A Pannon régióban, évelő kultúrákban a kaszálás a leggyakrabban alkalmazott gyomirtási technika. Inert- és élőmulcsot is alkalmaznak, valamint évelő talajtakaró növényeket. Ezeket a módszereket azért részesítik előnyben, mert könnyen beilleszthetők a hagyományos gazdálkodásba és minimális odafigyelést igényelnek, közvetlen előnyöket biztosítva a gazdálkodóknak. Sokan tudják, hogy szántással, szezonális takarónövényekkel és legeltetéssel is hatékonyan vissza lehet szorítani a gyomokat, de a legtöbben nem alkalmazzák ezeket a módszereket. A résztvevők a vegyes termesztést, talajtakarást és takarónövényeket hatékony gyomirtó stratégiáknak tekintik. A mulcsozás magas költsége azonban korlátozza az alkalmazását. Ezenkívül a válaszadók kiemelték a talajbarát gépi gyomirtási gyakorlatok és a géptervezés fejlesztésének szükségességét. A gyomirtó szerek helyettesítése is kiemelten fontos kérdés; olyan alternatív vegyszerek kifejlesztésére van szükség, amelyek kevésbé károsak a növényekre és az ökoszisztémákra. **AJÁNLÁS:** Olyan kísérlet felállítása, amely az ökológiai termelésben használható ökoszisztéma-barát gyakorlatokat, például a vegyes növénytermesztést (agrárerdészeti rendszerben), kombinálja a sorközi gyomirtással és hatékony, herbicideket kiváltó biológiai eredetű gyomirtószerrel használatával.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 16:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Steppic region (Ukraine)

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most popular and effective agroecological weed control methods used in the Steppic region in Ukraine?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS: Surveys and interviews with farmers reveal that crop rotation, inter-row cultivation and mechanical tillage are universally valued, with most of respondents emphasizing their importance. Additionally, over 98% recognize the value of qualitative seed material and competitive cultivars and hand weeding (85%). Practices that were popular in the past but are less common now include mowing, and grazing (over 70%). Mixed cropping and higher planting densities are less emphasized, with 40% and 25% of respondents respectively noting their decline. Methods like soil cover and flame weeding are known by 63% but used by few, with only 12% unfamiliar with these techniques.
RECOMMENDATION: Key agroecological strategies for effective weed control should include a well planned crop rotation to prevent soil depletion and pathogen accumulation, enhancing soil fertility with legumes mixed with mechanical tillage for maintaining soil structure, reducing erosion, and conserving moisture through practices like no-till and strip-till. Utilizing siderates and green manure steam as well as organic mulching for soil protection, moisture conservation, and weed suppression. For specific crops, strategies include optimizing tillage methods for winter wheat and corn, and combining stubble peeling with deep tillage for sunflowers. Integrated approaches combining mechanical, biological, and chemical methods are crucial for effective weed management and sustainable agriculture.

Short title in native language

Сприйняття стейкхолдерами найчастіше застосовуваних

Short summary for practitioners in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

ПРОБЛЕМА: Які найбільш популярні та ефективні агроекологічні методи боротьби з бур'янами використовуються в степовому регіоні України?

ДУМКА ЗАЦІКАВЛЕНИХ СТОРІН: Опитування та інтерв'ю з фермерами показують, що сівозмінна, міжрядна культивування та механічний обробіток ґрунту вважаються найдорцільнішими заходами. Крім того, понад 98% визнають цінність якісного насіннєвого матеріалу та конкурентоспроможних сортів (85%). Практики, які були популярні в минулому, але менш поширені зараз, включають косіння та випас (понад 70%). Менше уваги приділяється змішаним культурам і ущільненим посівам - 40% і 25% респондентів відповідно відзначають їх зниження. Ґрунтопокривні культури та вогнева прополка, відомі 63%, але використовуються не часто, а 12% не знайомі з цими методами.

РЕКОМЕНДАЦІЯ: Ключові агроекологічні стратегії для ефективного контролю бур'янів повинні включати добре сплановану сівозміну для запобігання виснаженню ґрунту та накопичення патогенів, підвищення родючості ґрунту за допомогою включення у сівозміну бобових культур, оптимальний механічний обробіток ґрунту для поліпшення структури ґрунту, зменшення ерозії та збереження вологи (нульовий та смуговий обробіток). Вдалими практиками є використання сидератів і зеленого добрива, а також органічне мульчування для захисту ґрунту, збереження вологи та пригнічення бур'янів. Для окремих культур стратегії включають оптимізацію методів обробітку ґрунту (для озимої пшениці та кукурудзи) та поєднання лущення стерні з глибоким обробітком ґрунту (для соняшнику). Інтегровані підходи, що поєднують механічні, біологічні та хімічні методи, мають вирішальне значення для ефективної боротьби з бур'янами та сталого сільського господарства.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 17:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in arable crops in Steppic region (Romania)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most popular and effective agroecological methods for weed control in arable crops in the steppic region (Romania)? **STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS:** Crop rotation emerges as the predominant agroecological method for weed control among farmers, with near-universal adoption. This is followed by the use of certified seed material and special sowing date with locally tested competitive varieties. Less frequently employed methods include weed maps and flame weeding, due to outdated technology for analogic weed maps and high costs associated with AI-based weed management solutions. Flame weeding is also less common in arable areas compared to vineyards and horticulture. Historically, hand weeding and high planting densities were more common but are now less favored due to reduced precipitation and labor shortages. Methods such as narrow rows and inter-row cultivation are known but not widely used. **RECOMMENDATION:** Focus on enhancing crop rotation practices, employing certified seeds, and utilizing competitive varieties to manage weeds effectively. Incorporate minimum tillage and mulching to improve soil health and reduce weed pressure. Update and integrate technologies like weed maps and explore flame weeding where feasible. Promote ongoing education and research to support these strategies and address practical challenges faced by farmers in the steppic region.

Short title in native language

Percepția părților interesate asupra celor mai frecvent utilizate metode

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

ÎNTREBARE: Care sunt cele mai populare și eficiente metode agroecologice de combatere a buruienilor în regiunea stepică (România)? **PERCEPȚIA PĂRȚILOR INTERESATE:** Rotația culturilor apare ca metodă agroecologică predominantă pentru controlul buruienilor în rândul fermierilor, cu adoptare aproape universală. Aceasta este urmată de utilizarea de semințe certificate și semănat în epocă specială, cu soiuri competitive, testate local. Metodele utilizate mai rar includ hărțile buruienilor și plivirea cu flacăra, din cauza neactualizării hărților pe suport analogic și a costurilor ridicate asociate cu soluțiile de identificare a buruienilor bazate pe inteligență artificială. Plivitul cu flacăra este, de asemenea, mai puțin utilizat în culturile arabile în comparație cu podgorii și horticultură. Din punct de vedere istoric, plivitul manual și densitățile mari de plantare au fost practicate, dar acum sunt mai puțin folosite din cauza penuriei de forță de muncă și a precipitațiilor reduse. Metode precum rândurile înguste și cultivarea între rânduri sunt cunoscute, dar nu sunt utilizate pe scară largă.

RECOMANDARE: Concentrați-vă pe îmbunătățirea practicilor de rotație a culturilor, utilizarea semințelor certificate și utilizarea soiurilor competitive pentru a gestiona eficient buruienile. Includeți lucrări minime de prelucrare a solului și mulcirea pentru a îmbunătăți sănătatea solului și pentru a reduce presiunea buruienilor. Actualizați și integrați tehnologii cum ar fi hărțile buruienilor și explorați plivitul cu flacăra acolo unde este posibil. Promovați educația și cercetarea continuă pentru a sprijini aceste strategii și pentru a aborda provocările practice cu care se confruntă fermierii din regiunea stepică.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 18:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in perennial crops (vineyards) in Steppic region (Romania)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) **outcomes** (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most common and effective agroecological methods for weed control in perennial crops in the steppe region?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTION: Farmers rely mainly on tillage, live mulches and cover crops. Although known, the Swiss Sandwich system and inert mulches are rarely used, along with thermal control and weed maps respectively. The parties concerned use extensive tillage, mowing, mulching and grazing, with intercropping also well known. Biological weed control is more common in vineyards, largely due to the added value of wine and the ecological trend. Manual weeding and manual hoeing are known for soil maintenance, encouraged by the trend of ecology but, increasing production costs and the need for additional labor, a scarce resource. Bioherbicides, although widely known, have produced limited results, causing farmers to doubt their effectiveness.
RECOMMENDATION: Agroecological management of weeds in vineyards should focus on increasing biological control that is effective and sustainable. Expanding the use of mechanical control such as tillage and mulching combined with newer methods such as thermal weed control should be a priority. Farmers should explore innovative techniques with systematic integration of grazing, intercropping and cover crops. Education and research are essential to address gaps and adopt diverse weed management strategies suited to regional conditions.

Short title in native language

Percepția părților interesate despre cele mai utilizate metode

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

ÎNTREBARE: Care sunt cele mai comune și eficiente metode agroecologice pentru combaterea buruienilor în culturile perene din regiunea stepică?

PERCEPȚIA PĂRȚILOR INTERESATE: Fermierii se bazează în principal pe lucrarea solului, mulci vii și culturi de acoperire. Deși cunoscute, sistemul *Swiss Sandwich* și mulciurile inerte sunt folosite rar, alături de controlul termic, respectiv hărțile buruienilor. Părțile interesate raportează folosirea pe scară largă a lucrărilor solului, cositul, mulcirea și pășunatul, cu culturile intercalate, de asemenea, binecunoscute. Combaterea biologică a buruienilor este mai frecventă în podgorii, în mare parte datorită valorii adăugate a vinului și a tendinței ecologice. Plivitul manual și prășitul manual sunt cunoscute pentru menținerea sănătății solului, încurajate de tendințele de ecologie dar, cresc costurile de producție și necesită forță de muncă suplimentară, resursă deficitară. Bioerbicidele, deși cunoscute pe scară largă, au dat rezultate limitate, făcând fermierii să se îndoiască de eficacitatea lor.

RECOMANDARE: Managementul agroecologic al buruienilor în podgorii ar trebui să se concentreze pe creșterea controlului biologic care este eficient și durabil. Extinderea utilizării controlului mecanic, cum ar fi lucrarea solului și mulcirea, combinată cu metode mai noi, cum ar fi combaterea termică a buruienilor, ar trebui să fie prioritare. Fermierii ar trebui să exploreze tehnici inovatoare, cu integrarea sistematică a pășunatului, a culturilor intercalate și a culturilor de acoperire. Educația și cercetarea sunt esențiale pentru a aborda lacunele și pentru a îmbunătăți adoptarea diverselor strategii de combatere a buruienilor potrivite condițiilor regionale.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 19:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in alpine region (Poland)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: what is the most popular and frequently used agroecological method of weed control in the alpine region? **STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS** Among surveyed farmers from Poland's alpine region, crop rotation is the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control. It is advised by 83% of surveyed farmers. The use of certified seed is also very popular, with 75% of respondents using it. Less popular are inter-row cultivation (31%), special planting dates (28%), and competitive cultivars (28%). One-quarter of the respondents used mowing, grazing, and hand weeding. Respondents were also asked about weed control methods used by farmers in the past, but they no longer use them. Half of the respondents indicated mixed cropping. Approximately 1/5 of the respondents no longer use high planting densities. Among the methods that farmers had heard about but never used, the most common were soil cover and flame weeding (69%), inter-row cultivation (64%), narrow rows (64%), and weed maps (61%). **RECOMMENDATION:** Properly designed crop rotation, comprising ca. 50% of cereals and a composition of winter and spring crops, is the most reliable method to keep agricultural pests, including weeds, under control. Crop rotation can also improve soil physical and chemical qualities, especially when legumes and other deeply rooted crops are included. It substantially adds to above- and below-ground biodiversity in an agricultural landscape. There is a need to research, advise, and keep farmers informed about the qualities of crop rotation to steer agriculture toward profitable and sustainable production systems.

Short title in native language

Zdaniem rolników płodozmian to najpopularniejsza agroekologiczna

Short summary for practitioners in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: jaka jest najpopularniejsza i najczęściej stosowana agroekologiczna metoda ograniczania zachwaszczenia w regionie alpejskim? **ZDANIEM ROLNIKÓW** Wśród ankietowanych rolników z regionu alpejskiego w Polsce, płodozmian jest najczęściej stosowaną agroekologiczną metodą ograniczania zachwaszczenia. Zaleca go 83% ankietowanych osób. Stosowanie kwalifikowanego materiału siewnego jest również bardzo popularne, stosuje go 75% respondentów. Mniej popularne są pielęgnacja międzyrzędzi (31%), opóźnione terminy siewu (28%) i dobór odpowiednich, bardziej konkurencyjnych odmian (28%). Jedna czwarta respondentów stosowała koszenie, wypasanie i ręczne pielenie. Respondentów zapytano również o metody zwalczania chwastów stosowane przez rolników w przeszłości, ale nie obecnie. Połowa respondentów wskazała siewy mieszane. Około 1/5 respondentów nie stosuje już zwiększonej gęstości siewu. Wśród metod, o których słyszeli rolnicy, ale ich nie stosowali, najczęstsze były: odchwaszczanie płomieniowe (69%), pielęgnacja międzyrzędzi (64%), zmniejszenie szerokości międzyrzędzi (64%) i mapowanie chwastów (61%). **ZALECENIE:** Prawidłowo zaprojektowany płodozmian, obejmujący ok. 50% zbóż ozimych i jarych, i 50% innych gatunków roślin uprawnych, jest najpewniejszą metodą kontrolowania agrofagów, w tym chwastów. Poprawnie skonstruowany płodozmian poprawi właściwości fizyczne i chemiczne gleby, zwłaszcza gdy włączy się do niego rośliny bobowate i gatunki o głębokim systemie korzeniowym. Płodozmian w znacznym stopniu zwiększa nadziemną i podziemną bioróżnorodność. Istnieje potrzeba badań, doradztwa i informowania rolników o znaczeniu płodozmianu w zrównoważonych systemach produkcji rolniczej.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 20:

Short title in English

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in arable crops in Continental region (Poland)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: What are the most common and effective agroecological methods for weed control in arable crops in the continental region?
STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS: Crop rotation is the most frequently used agroecological method, with nearly 90% of farmers adopting it. The use of certified seed material follows closely at 85%, while around 50% of farmers use special sowing dates, and about 40% employ competitive varieties. Less common methods include weed maps, tillage, cover crops, and flame weeding. Traditional practices like mixed cropping and hand weeding have largely been abandoned, and methods such as inter-row cultivation and tillage are known but seldom practiced. Notably, weed maps are the least familiar method, unknown to 35% of farmers. Stakeholders agree on the importance of crop rotation, inter-row cultivation, and hand weeding, with over 90% awareness of these techniques. Additionally, certified seeds, cover crops, and mulching are recognized by 87% of stakeholders, while mowing and grazing are acknowledged by 82%.

RECOMMENDATION: Agroecological weed control should focus on promoting successful practices like crop rotation and certified seed material while increasing adoption of underutilized methods, such as weed maps and cover crops. Emphasis should be placed on integrating mechanical control methods, like shallow plowing and inter-row cultivation, with innovative technologies, including laser weeding and robots. Preventive strategies, such as using qualified seed material and understanding weed biology, should be prioritized to enhance crop competitiveness. Education and research are essential to improving the adoption of these methods and addressing gaps in farmer knowledge.

Short title in native language

Spostrzeżenia interesariuszy w zakresie najczęściej wykorzystywanych

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

PROBLEM: jaka jest najefektywniejsza i najczęściej stosowana agroekologiczna metoda ograniczania zachwaszczenia w regionie kontynentalnym?

ZDANIEM ROLNIKÓW Wśród ankietowanych rolników z regionu kontynentalnego, najczęściej stosowaną agroekologiczną metodą ograniczania zachwaszczenia w Polsce jest płodozmian. Stosuje go 90% ankietowanych osób. Stosowanie kwalifikowanego materiału siewnego jest również bardzo popularne, stosuje go 85% respondentów. Dość popularne są także wcześniejsze terminy siewu (50%) i dobór odpowiednich, bardziej konkurencyjnych odmian (40%). Mniej popularne są takie metody jak mapy chwastów, rośliny okrywowe oraz odchwaszczanie płomieniowe. Tradycyjne metody walki z zachwaszczeniem jak zasiewy mieszane czy pielenie ręczne nie są stosowane, natomiast takie metody jak pielęgnacja międzyrzędzi są znane, ale stosowane rzadko. Warto zauważyć, że mapy chwastów są najmniej znaną metodą walki z zachwaszczeniem, metody tej nie zna 35% badanych rolników.

ZALECENIE Zasadne jest promowanie mniej znanych a skutecznych agroekologicznych metod regulacji zachwaszczenia, jak mapy chwastów czy stosowanie roślin okrywowych. Należy położyć nacisk na integrację metod mechanicznej kontroli chwastów, jak płytki orki i uprawa międzyrzędowa, z innowacyjnymi technologiami, w tym odchwaszczaniem laserowym i robotami. Strategie prewencyjne walki z zachwaszczeniem, takie jak stosowanie kwalifikowanego materiału siewnego, bądź znajomość biologii chwastów, powinny być traktowane priorytetowo w celu zwiększenia konkurencyjności upraw. Edukacja i badania są niezbędne do poprawy wdrażania tych metod i zachęcenia rolników do ich stosowania.